

Effect of the Nature and Concentration of the Supporting Electrolyte on the Half-wave Potential and Diffusion Current. Part II

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The diffusion current and half-wave potentials have been measured at different concentrations of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions in presence of different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes KCl , KNO_3 , NH_4Cl , and CaCl_2 . Both these parameters exhibit variations which could not be accounted for by changes in viscosity alone. An attempt has been made to explain the observations in the light of the influence of (1) ionic strength, (2) interionic forces, and (3) the hydrogen overvoltage.

In a previous communication¹ the effect of the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolyte on the half-wave potential and diffusion current of Cd and Zn ions was discussed. The products, $i_d\tau$, were found to vary with the variation of concentration of the supporting electrolytes. A systematic increase of the product definitely shows that there are some other factors appearing which may be responsible for the disproportionate increase in i_d , because a mere change in viscosity has been found to have no complicating influence².

In the present communication our object has been to study the influence of variation of the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolytes in the case of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions and to examine whether any complicating factors arise in such cases too.

EXPERIMENTAL

The present study is confined to the cases of the reducing ions, Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} only, with the supporting electrolytes KCl , KNO_3 , NH_4Cl , and CaCl_2 . Chemicals used were all of G.R. quality of E. Merck. The instrument used and the experimental conditions were the same as in Part I¹. Results are recorded in Tables I and II.

DISCUSSION

Ni²⁺ as the Reducing Ion

The case of Ni^{2+} as the reducing ion has been presented at two different temperatures (30° and 35°) in Table I (A and B). Concentrations of Ni used were $10^{-4}M$ (at 30°) and $10^{-3}M$ (at 35°). At the lower concentration it has been observed (with KCl , KNO_3 , and NH_4Cl at 30°) that the diffusion current (i_d) diminishes consistently as the concentrations of these supporting electrolytes increase from 0.1 to $2M$. The change appears to

1. Mukherjee and Chakravarti, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 995.
2. *Idem.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 77.

TABLE I

*Nickel(ous) ions.*A. Conc. = 1×10^{-4} M. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Supporting electrolyte. Conc.	KCl		KNO ₃		NH ₄ Cl							
	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Rel. viscosity (η).	id.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	η .	id.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	η .	id.			
0.1M	1.313 μ s	1.108 volt	1.000	1.313	1.236 μ s	1.118 volts	0.997	1.236	1.500 μ s	1.041 volts	1.000	1.600
0.5	1.444	1.088	0.995	1.141	1.106	1.118	0.987	1.098	1.050	1.048	0.999	1.050
1.0	0.825	1.098	0.976	0.815	0.900	1.103	0.970	0.866	0.713	1.073	0.999	0.713
2.0	0.760	1.108	0.962	0.736	0.788	1.058	0.956	0.772	0.563	1.053	0.994	0.561
3.5	0.245	1.040	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..

B. Conc. = 1×10^{-3} M. Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Supporting electrolyte. Conc.	KCl		KNO ₃		NH ₄ Cl		Supporting electrolyte. Conc.		CaCl ₂			
	id.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	id.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	id.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	id.	Conc.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	η .	id.	η .
0.1M	8.760 μ s	1.00 volts	10.25 μ s	1.00 volts	7.00 μ s	1.00 volts	0.05M	7.00 μ s	1.098 volts	0.994	6.978	6.978
0.5	8.000	1.03	8.75	1.04	5.25	1.06	0.1	5.75	1.058	1.026	5.840	5.840
1.5	6.260	1.04	7.25	1.04	4.80	1.04	0.5	4.37	1.058	1.112	4.607	4.607
2.0	5.125	1.04	5.75	1.05	3.38	1.04	1.0	3.75	1.058	1.249	4.191	4.191
							2.0	1.65	1.020	1.593	2.083	2.083
							3.2	1.35	0.918	..	..	..
							4.4	0.825	0.838	..	..	..

TABLE II
Cobalt(ous) ions.

Supporting electrolyte. Conc.	KCl		KNO ₃		NH ₄ Cl	
	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$i_{d\frac{1}{2}}$	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$i_{d\frac{1}{2}}$	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	$i_{d\frac{1}{2}}$
0.1M	0.630 μ s	1.110 volts	1.001	0.630	..	..
0.5	0.650	1.110	0.993	0.648	0.575 μ s	1.090 volts
1.0	0.665	1.090	0.986	0.660	0.600	1.090
2.0	0.675	1.090	0.981	0.669	0.650	1.098
					0.632	0.632
					0.825 μ s	1.300 volts
					0.600	1.280
					..	..
					..	..
					..	..
0.1	4.000	1.13	..	..	4.125	1.200
0.5	4.125	1.15	..	..	4.125	1.340
1.0	4.124	1.21	..	..	4.125	1.360
2.0	3.875	1.23	..	..	4.125	1.370

A. Conc. = 1×10^{-4} M. Temp. = $30^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$.

B. Conc. = 1×10^{-3} M. Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$.

be maximum in the case of NH_4Cl . From the nature of the changes in η (relative viscosity) in such cases (as shown in the column for η), the diffusion current is expected to show a corresponding and proportionate increase. The slight increase of η in the case of CaCl_2 solutions (Table I, B) should bring about a proportionate diminution of the diffusion current, but as from the last column the product ($i_d \eta^{1/2}$), which should ordinarily remain constant, appears to diminish steadily and rapidly. All these facts suggest that there are some other factors (besides viscosity) which influence the magnitude of the diffusion current and the half-wave potential also.

The half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) after i_R correction, presented in a separate column in each case, practically remains constant although the concentrations of the supporting electrolytes are increased excepting in the case of KNO_3 (with $10^{-4}M$ at 30°) and CaCl_2 (with $10^{-3}M$ at 35°) where there has been continuous and steady diminution (of the negative potential) with increase in salt concentration. With KCl too (at $10^{-4}M$ at 30°), there has been a marked diminution of the negative value of $E_{1/2}$ and of i_d at a concentration of $3.5 M$ of KCl . The observations in the case of CaCl_2 are in accord with those of Pavlik⁵.

An explanation of the observations, noted above, may be attempted if we remember the various factors which exert influence in such cases.

Firstly, the effect of the ionic strength is of foremost importance in such cases. It is well known that ionic strength influences the interionic forces and the ionic mobility and consequently the diffusion coefficient and the diffusion current. The higher the ionic strength, greater is the interionic attraction and the lower becomes the ionic mobility, which is a well-known fact⁶. The diffusion coefficient, D , which is related to the ionic mobility by the equation:

$$\frac{1}{D} = \left(\frac{1}{u_+} + \frac{1}{u_-} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2RT}$$

is also expected to vary with the variation of the latter⁹. In the light of these considerations a diminution of the diffusion current (i_d) is to be expected along with an increase in the concentration of the supporting electrolyte. Moreover, ionic strength also affects the values of $E_{1/2}$, as noted by Kolthoff and Lingane¹⁰. But the more marked diminutions, as observed with higher chlorine-ion concentrations ($3.5M\text{-KCl}$ and $4.4M\text{-CaCl}_2$), appear to be the probable outcome of some additional factors besides the ionic strength.

The Ni^{2+} ions are believed to remain in aqueous solutions forming complexes with H_2O molecules. These aquo-complexes are gradually depleted (water molecules being gradually replaced by chlorine ions) at higher chloride ion concentrations⁴. The relationship of this phenomenon with the changes in $E_{1/2}$ may be understood if we remember that the higher negative values of $E_{1/2}$, which clearly indicate irreversible deposition of Ni^{2+} from dilute

3. De Ford and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3918.

4. Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography", Vol. II, p. 486, Interscience Publishers, N.Y., 1952.

5. Pavlik, *Chem. Abst.*, 1931, **25**, 3902.

6. Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography", Vol. I, p. 61, Interscience Publishers, N.Y., 1952.

7. Willis *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1680.

8. Lingane and Herbinger, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1941, **13**, 17.

9. Nernst, "Theoretical Chemistry", Eng. Translation by Codd, 1923, McMillan & Co, p. 436.

10. Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography", Vol. I, p. 197.

solutions, is explained as the outcome of slow and slight dehydration of Ni^{2+} ions (specially in the case of CaCl_2), which remain hydrated in the inner sphere of co-ordination, whereas the lower values of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (more positive values), which indicate more reversible deposition in concentrated solutions, are supposed to occur from the complex $(\text{NiCl}_4)^{2-}$ formed in the solution by the dehydration of hydrated Ni^{2+} ions and penetration of the Cl^- ions into the inner co-ordination sphere.

In addition to this, considerations of overvoltage may also be conveniently involved in such cases.

Ni has a higher hydrogen overvoltage and it is expected to require greater negative potential to become converted from Ni^{2+} to Ni metal. With the formation of complexes, this overvoltage will of course undergo change; it is quite likely that it diminishes and consequently lowers the value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and shifts it to the more positive side¹¹.

The behaviour of Ni at the higher concentration ($10^{-3}M$) is almost similar to that at the lower concentration ($10^{-4}M$). Rise of temperature from 30° to 35° appears to have very little effect on $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ excepting that at the higher temperature it diminishes a little which is normally expected due to the irreversible reduction of the reducing ion.

Co²⁺ as the Reducing Ion

The results of study with the Co^{2+} ion and different supporting electrolytes, viz., KCl, KNO_3 , and NH_4Cl , are given in Table II(A and B).

Kolthoff and Lingane (vide ref. No. 4, p. 480) have reported a half-wave potential of -1.4 volts in the case of hexaquo-cobaltous ion in the non-complexing supporting electrolyte like KCl against the saturated calomel electrode⁷. Lingane and Herbringer⁸ report the same to be -1.2 volts at 25° in $1M$ -KCl. Our observations, however, show a value of -1.09 and -1.21 volts with concentrations of 10^{-4} and $10^{-3}M$ at 30° and 35° , respectively, under the same conditions. At the higher concentration of Co^{2+} , $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ appears to increase slightly with increasing concentration of KCl, but at the lower concentration ($10^{-4}M$) it shows practically no tendency to change. Increase of temperature indicates a slight increase of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (more negative). How far this is due to the changed reversibility of the reducing ion, which may occur at the higher temperature, is, however, not known.

The diffusion current increases slightly with increasing concentrations of KCl and KNO_3 (at Co^{2+} conc. $10^{-4}M$). With two concentrations of NH_4Cl studied ($1.0M$ and $0.5M$), the value of i_d tends to diminish with increasing NH_4Cl concentration. With $10^{-4}M$ of Co^{2+} , the study of higher concentrations of NH_4Cl was not possible as it tended to yield erratic results.

With KCl and KNO_3 , $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ appears to show slight changes with concentrations for both the Co^{2+} ion concentrations. With NH_4Cl similar changes are observed. In the latter case, the observations may be attributed to the probable complex formation, but in the cases of KCl and KNO_3 for the slight increase of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, other factors like the influence of ionic strength, etc. might be invoked. The exact explanation is not yet clear.

11. Lingane, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 1.

The values recorded here compare excellently with those of Willis *et al.*⁷. The half-wave potentials of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} are very close together in KCl and KNO_3 , but not so with NH_4Cl .

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